

PLACE OF METHODS OF KNOWLEDGE IN THE SCIENTIFIC SYSTEM

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Introduction. In the XXI st century, when the achievements of science are increasingly expanding and deepen the cognitive opportunities of a person, as ever is sharply the question of the further creative development of the methodology of scientific knowledge. It is based on it is progress in all areas of science. This fully refers to philosophy, its kernel - dialectics. Science has become one of the most powerful engines of social research methods of scientific knowledge, the mechanism of their functioning in obtaining new knowledge, has gained special significance. The need for a clear and strict methodology is particularly acute currently, when accurate forecasts and competent actions are required by the scientific community, specialists of various areas of knowledge. The systematic development of such an essential incommutation, as a method, is necessary both for the normal functioning of scientific theories and the general methodology of cognition - dialectics, interaction, the mutual penetration of which ensures the truth and comprehensiveness of knowledge. Logical, historical, coherent and objective methods of scientific knowledge were widely used in the analysis of this article. An analysis of the role of cognitive methods in the scientific system was conducted. P.V. Kopnun's textbook, "The problem of dialectics as logic and the theory of knowledge, was identified as a methodological resource.

Place of method in the scientific system. In modern conditions for the continuous formation of new knowledge systems, new research methods arise problems that require additional analysis of the concepts of the method and those of its aspects that are associated with the mechanism of interaction between the general methodology and special-scientific analogs, typology of methods. It is known that the result of all scientific research is the emergence of new theoretical knowledge, a new theory. The concept of the theory as who has become formed knowledge implies existence in its content of pure, reliable knowledge free from random, sidelines and components of knowledge. Therefore, under reliable, East The creation and development of scientific theory is not for scientific

knowledge the only and ultimate goal. Scientific theory is needed in order to be a method of practical and cognitive activity. That is, the theory acts as the main source platform in the formation and operation of the scientific method. In the history of human thought, the methods arose and arise as a result of creating new theories. The dialectical interconnection of the theory and method, the negligible leading of the method from the content of scientific theory will prevent the principles, laws and logical connections that form scientific theory. The scientific method exists not only as a job, but also as a form of knowledge, and the specifics of the scientific method is that it is not only knowledge, but also the mechanism, obtaining new knowledge. For any law, reflecting reality, also indicates how to think. Being moving, the proof of the principle as the method of knowledge. The problem of the scientific research method is complex, computers. The scientific method is a theory, but only in action facing outside.

There are no special principles and laws in the structure of the method other than the principles and laws of the initial theory. All those principles and laws of scientific theory that have a methodological value are included in the structure of the scientific method. The methodological function of the theory is as it were, within the framework of which the principles and laws of scientific theory acquire all new qualities, in particular the quality of the method. The other functions of scientific theory, in the frequency, It is difficult to agree with the statement of some scientists that the scientific theory is only the prerequisite of the method, but not the method itself. In their opinion, the theory of dialectics included in it the laws and categories themselves without any transformations into the requirements regulating cognitive activities cannot play a methodological role, as well as the theoretical provisions of specific sciences expressing which -Lo laws, principles. P.V. Kopnin, who believes "when the attitude of the principles, laws of philosophy to the phenomena of the material world, it turns out their objective content, then they act as knowledge about being being. When their role (principles and laws) is determined in the process of thinking and practical activity, they act as a method of achieving new results. "[1.c.109.]Understanding the method and the theory of dialectics in the organic odd is the most faithful in philosophical literature. A vivid confirmation of the word I.D.andreyev: " The organic unity of the theory and method of philosophy directly follows from the provision on the unity (identity) of dialectics, logic and the theory of knowledge ". [2.c.254.] The strength of one or another method, that is, the provision of objectively obtained, and the transformed knowledge and implementation of certain functions of the method depends on the content, the depth

of the theory, which includes on which it is applied. Methods - Conceptual explanatory, predictive indirectly help the methodological function of scientific theory. Funds and operational apparatus - become affective only as elements of a certain theory. Understanding and productive use of one or another method is possible in the composition and on the basis of the theory or several joint theories that have a task. Many mistakes are a consequence that one or another method was applied regardless of the theory, due to only common sense and general ideas about the method. Attracting the concept of "theory" and its structural elements when determining the It shows that there are no fundamental differences between theoretical knowledge and method. The concept of the identity of the method and the theory pretends to sufficiently fully reproduce the nature of the method, but does not reach its concept "method" is correct and justified. In any case, the initial point of the method of scientific knowledge is objective reality. The method acts as a method of operating by the existing scientific materials, so it cannot be somehow artificial, a priori destination or condition. The method is an expression of the main coordination of the mined knowledge, its principle feature. And yet the method, being interrelated with scientific theory, has relative independence and occupies a specific place in the methodology where, along with the method, and the techniques, funds, operations and their techniques are also included. In a scientific study, the latter plays or an auxiliary role in the disease, or part of the components, elements in the maintenance of the scientific method.

Therefore, it can be confident that the scientific method is a more complex education than the tool, reception, rule. There is a significant difference between the method and theory. The structure of the theory includes, as is known, as the main components, a system of fundamental concepts, a system of laws of varying degrees of community and the system of principles also of various degrees of common and occupying various places in the structure of the theory, depending on whether they are Initial, meaningful or formal. All of these components in such an extent and in such a form as these occur in theory, the content of the method is not included. There is a significant difference between the method and theory.

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system of rules, principles, techniques, norms, installations orienting person in various types of its activities, given by Descartes: "Under the method ... I understand accurate and simple rules, the strict adherence to which always prevents the adoption of false for true and, Without unnecessary spending of mental strength, but gradually and continuously increasing knowledge, contributes to the fact that the mind reaches true knowledge of everything that is available to him. And then Descartes notes: the whole method is in order and place the placement of what should be sent to the point of mind in order to open any truth.

The method characterizes primarily the technology of scientific cognition, the laws of its own development. Since this activity itself is multifaceted, the method can be understood in various meanings: 1) as a way of cognitive activity; 2) as the rules, prescriptions of this activity; 3) as theories, laws that are used to select and organize a method of activity and its own and to formulate relevant rules for this activity **The system of true knowledge of the subjective and objective in the method.** The method is not an arbitrary logical design. It is formulated and developed on the basis of the knowledge of the patterns of the studied area of reality, in accordance with the essence, and contain the studied phenomena, which makes its mandatory connection with theory. Therefore, undoubtedly, Hegel's rights, when the method is considered as a method of internal self-saturation content. In the method of scientific knowledge, the basis of which is the system of true knowledge, which reveals the patterns of a cognitive object, these negotiations are transformed into rules and techniques of the subject. Therefore, its objective and subjective sides are organically interrelated in the scientific method. The subjectivity of the method is determined in the first turn by the fact that it is the result of activity, creative activity of the subject. The objectivity of the method is due to the fact that this is a way to assign an object that it is based on knowledge, the content of which is objectively. This relationship of the subjective and objective in the method is fixed in the method of determining the method. So, P. V. Kopnin noted: "Under the method, we understand this method of human activity, in which the advanced objective discominations are together with the focus on the knowledge of the object and its preformation. [5.C.84] is therefore The content of any method is not only certain methods of logical operations that ensure the achievement of the goal, but those and those general principles from which these techniques follow and which regulate the process of cognition and practical action. Therefore, the results of cognition depend not only on the nature and properties of the object being studied, but also from the tools that are used. Miscellaneous approaches and methods will lead to different

reconstruction of the same system object. The content of knowledge in the final consumption is determined by the content, nature and specificity, the nature of the item itself. Therefore, cognitive actions with it cannot be completely independent of the nature of the subject of study. The theory of reflection justifies the provision that true knowledge can be obtained only if the proceedler builds its activities as it is required: i) the characteristic of the object being studied; 2) the objective of the study; 3) the conditions in which it proceeds. If this activity relies on a specific scientific method, adequate to las and objectives of the study.

Conclusion. The results of scientific knowledge are continuously in the search for new methods in their systematization. Moreover, it's not so much in a simple update of research methods and formal logical classifications that do not lead to effective, high quality shifts in knowledge, as in finding such methods and systems of methods, with which you can It would be used to explore the object in development from different parties, with all its connections . In general, the combination and nature of the methods used in science is determined by common for all cognition by laws, as well as the subject of this science and its place in the system of scientific knowledge. Each of the scientific methods not only reveals the verge of the universal philosophical method, but also enriches its content. The philosophical method is refracted, it is specified and implemented through all the methods of science, through the entire totality of scientific knowledge. From the above it follows that the method has its own determination in objective reality and its patterns, but at the same time he is subordinated to the subjective strength of human consciousness. The method from the beginning and to the end there is an ideal phenomenon, it prevents the ideal means of knowledge. The method is something secondary with respect to objective and real laws with respect to independent functions. It, as their subjective analogue, is not only for explanation, but also to change the act. In these functions of the method, its creative force is revealed as the movement of the human, phenomenon to achieving objective truth.

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